

Sanctuary of Hera in the Argolid

also known as “Argive Heraion”

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Entry tags: Archaeological Site, Ancient Mediterranean, Religious Group, Ritual centre, Polytheistic, Greek Religions, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Temenos, Sacred Enclosure, Graeco-Roman, Indo-European Religion, Aegean, Greek Cult, Religious Place, Temple, Altar, Greece, Hill, Archaeological monument

The Sanctuary of Hera in the Argolid contains archaeological material dating to the Late Bronze Age and was likely a Mycenaean cult area. In the Archaic Period, the temenos and sanctuary were expanded and a wooden temple of Hera was constructed. In the 7th through 5th centuries, the city-states of Mycenae, Tiryns, and Argos co-managed the sanctuary. In the 460s BCE Argos achieved mastery over the sanctuary after destroying Mycenae and Tiryns, and by the middle of the 5th century BCE the sanctuary entered into a new phase of construction and monumentalization. From this time on, the sanctuary came to represent the worldview of Argos and its festival of Hera achieved broad renown. The sanctuary experienced a devastating fire that destroyed the Archaic Temple, but a replacement temple was already in the works and completed no later than the 390s BCE. This temple was still standing when the Roman-era Greek traveler Pausanias visited the site in the middle of the 2nd century CE. The sanctuary probably fell out of use sometime after the sack of the Visigoths at the end of the 4th century CE.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 400 CE

Region: The Sanctuary of Hera in the Argolid

Region tags: Greece

The Sanctuary of Hera in the Argolid including the Archaic and Classical terraces.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Christopher A. Pfaff, *The Argive Heraion 1: The Architecture of the Classical Temple of Hera* (Princeton: American School of Classical Studies at Athens, 2003)
- Source 2: Richard A. Tomlinson, *Argos and the Argolid from the End of the Bronze Age to the Roman Occupation* (London: Routledge, 1972)
- Source 3: Carla M. Antonaccio, "Terraces, tombs, and the early Argive Heraion." *Hesperia: The Journal of the American School of Classical Studies at Athens* 61, no. 1 (1992): 85-105.
- Source 1: François De Polignac, *Cults, Territory, and the Origins of the Greek City-State* (Chicago:

University of Chicago Press, 1995)

- Source 2: Marer-Banasik, Elizabeth Anne. The archaic pottery from the Argive Heraion excavations: typology, chronology and aspects of regionality. Ph.D. diss.: Indiana University, 1997.
- Source 3: Pfaff, Christopher A. The Argive Heraion: the architecture of the Classical Temple of Hera. Ph.D. diss.: New York University, 1992.
- Source 1: Charles Waldstein et al., The Argive Heraion. 2 vols. (1902 & 1905 Boston & New York)
- Source 2: Pierre Amandry, "Observations sur les monuments de l'Héraion d'Argos," *Hesperia: The Journal of the American School of Classical Studies at Athens* 21 (1952) 222-274
- Source 3: Jonathan M. Hall, "How Argive Was the "Argive" Heraion? The Political and Cultic Geography of the Argive Plain, 900-400 BC." *American Journal of Archaeology* 99, no. 4 (1995): 577-613.
- Source 1: Strøm, Ingrid. "The early sanctuary of the Argive Heraion and its external relations (8th-early 6th cent. B.C.): the monumental architecture." *Acta Archaeologica* 59 (1988): 173-203.
- Source 2: Mason, R. S. Architectural problems of the Argive Heraion. The northeast building and neighboring structures. Ph.D. diss: University of North Carolina Chapel Hill, 1979.
- Source 3: Coulton, John James. "The columns and roof of the south stoa at the Argive Heraion." *Annual of the British School at Athens* LXVIII (1973): 65-85.
- Source 1: Miller, Stephen G. "The date of the west building at the Argive Heraion." *American Journal of Archaeology* LXXVII (1973): 9-18.
- Source 2: Caskey, John L. and Amandry, Pierre. "Investigations at the Heraion of Argos, 1949." *Hesperia* XXI (1952): 165-221.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.argolisculture.gr/en/list-of-monuments/archaeological-site-of-heraion-argos/>
- Source 1 Description: Website of the Ephorate of Antiquities of Argolida

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The Heraion was first discovered by General Thomas Gordon in 1831 who excavated in 1838. C Bursian and R. A. Rangavis (1854), Heinrich Schliemann (1874) and Panagiotis Stamatakis (1878) each excavated a single season. The American School of Classical Studies at Athens conducted major excavations under Charles Waldstein (1892-1895) and Carl Blegen (1925-1928). John L. Caskey and Pierre Amandry excavated from 1947-1949 in a collaboration between the French and American Archaeological Schools.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1838, 1854, 1874, 1878, 1892-1895, 1925-1928, 1947-1949

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Το Ηράίο του Άργους

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: Mt. Euboea

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

Notes: There are three distinct monumental terraces at the sanctuary.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The city-state of Argos was 10km to the southwest and Mycenae was 8km to the northwest.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Construction at the Heraion took place in several phases. The first phase can be considered the monumental upper terrace upon which the Archaic Temple of Hera was built. The second phase occurred in the middle of the 5th century under the direction of Argos, which included the Classical Temple of Hera, three stoai, the West Building (a hestiatorion/dining facility), the monumental staircase between the lower and middle terraces, the East and Northwest Buildings, and the Classical Temple of Hera. The Gymnasium (Lower Stoa) probably dates to 4th century BCE. There is also Roman-era bath complex.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: A fire burned the Archaic Temple of Hera in 423 BCE, but a replacement temple was rebuilt. The rest of the sanctuary seems to have gone out of use around the end of the 4th century CE.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of pillage

Notes: The sanctuary of Hera might have been overrun and pillaged by invading Visigoths at the end of the 4th century CE.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Excavations have revealed the foundations of many buildings, as well as

monumental staircases and terracing, that are now visible. No significant reconstructions of ancient buildings have taken place.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Hera

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Argos

Notes: It is debated in scholarly literature about the extent to which Greek city-states of the Argive plain contributed to the construction of the Heraion before the mid-5th century BCE. Once Argos destroyed Tiryns and Mycenae, Argos possessed sole control over the sanctuary.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Hera

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: To commemorate a mythological event

Notes: The well-known story of Io being turned into a cow by Zeus to hide her from his wife Hera apparently took place in this area (ps.-Apollodorus, Library, 2.1.3).

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 790

Notes: The largest building was the Classical Temple of Hera which measured 39.5m x 20m, but the largest human construction was the upper ("Old") terrace, which held the Archaic Temple of Hera measuring 55.80m x 34.40m.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: The creation of the three terraces required the removal and moving of many tons of

earth.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

Notes: The Archaic Temple of Hera on the upper ("Old") terrace was probably built out of wood but is no longer extant.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: The retaining walls for the upper ("Old") terrace was made of stone in the style of "Cyclopean" masonry. The buildings of the sanctuary were made of marble superstructures and conglomerate stone foundations.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias (2.17.3) describes the pediment sculptures of the Classical Temple of Hera: "The sculptures carved above the pillars refer either to the birth of Zeus and the battle between the gods and the giants, or to the Trojan war and the capture of Ilium."

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias' description (2.17.4, 2.17.6) records that cuckoos and peacocks were present in relief images.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias (2.17.4-5) describes the cult statue of Hera: "The statue of Hera is seated on a throne; it is huge, made of gold and ivory, and is a work of Polycleitus. She is wearing a crown with Graces and Seasons worked upon it, and in one hand she carries a pomegranate and in the other a sceptre. About the pomegranate I must say nothing, for its story is somewhat of a holy mystery. The presence of a cuckoo seated on the sceptre they explain by the story that when Zeus was in love with Hera in her maidenhood he changed himself into this bird, and she caught it to be her pet. This tale and similar legends about the gods I relate without believing them, but I relate them nevertheless. By the side of Hera stands what is said to be an image of Hebe fashioned by Naucydes; it, too, is of ivory and gold. By its side is an old image of Hera on a pillar. The oldest image is made of wild-pear wood, and was dedicated in Tiryns by Peirasus, son of Argus, and when the Argives destroyed Tiryns they carried it away to the Heraeum. I myself saw it, a small, seated image.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias (2.17.3) states that "in the fore-temple are on the one side ancient statues of the Graces," and at 2.17.6 Pausanias states that "There is an altar upon which is wrought in relief the fabled marriage of Hebe and Heracles."

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias (2.17.3) states that "Before the entrance stand statues of women who have been priestesses to Hera and of various heroes, including Orestes. They say that Orestes is the one with the inscription, that it represents the Emperor Augustus."

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias (2.17.3) relates that the themes of the marble reliefs on the pediments of the Classical Temple of Hera: "The sculptures carved above the pillars refer either to the birth of Zeus and the battle between the gods and the giants, or to the Trojan war and the capture of Ilium."

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Notes: As with all ancient Greek temples, marble surfaces would have been painted, but no such examples are extant.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Notes: There are inscriptions found at the sanctuary, but none that could be described as decoration.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: N/A

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: The nearby site of Prosymna contained burials from the Bronze Age to Geometric periods.

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Zeus is only present as the consort of Hera. He is not the main deity worshiped at the sanctuary.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Zeus is the consort of Hera

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Numerous votive dedications at the sanctuary indicate offerings to the Hera (and/or other gods) in supplication or for thanksgiving.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Several thousands
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Annually (at a minimum)
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Wine

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Yes [specify]: Cattle
- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No
- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Bronze fibulae (broaches) were excavated in mass quantities, as well as numerous hydria (small water vessels).

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Statuettes, seals, vases, pottery, scarabs, various tools, glass, porcelain, and amber beads, gold and silver ornaments, terracotta, ivories, etc.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Permanent staff are unknown at this sanctuary, but women who served life appointments as priestesses of Hera probably lived nearby.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Yes

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Yes

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marriage

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: There was an annual hecatomb sacrifice in honor of Hera.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Field doesn't know

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: The West Building has been identified as a dining facility

Notes: Stephen G. Miller 1973. "The Date of the West Building at the Argive Heraion." *American Journal of Archaeology* 77, no. 1: 9-18.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual and quadrennial

Notes: Two main festivals took place at the Heraion, the Hecatombaia and Heraia, both in honor of Hera. The earliest evidence for the Hecatombaia is from the early 5th century BCE. As Pierre Amandry has noted (1980), the Hecatombaia festival was probably renamed the Heraia in the early 3rd century BCE. The Heraia would have taken place every four years in the beginning of June. A smaller, annual Hecatombaia would have likewise taken place in the early summer. Pierre Amandry, 1980. "Sur les concours argiens," *Études argiennes* (BCH Supplement 6): 211-253.

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members
- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: Several thousands
- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned

with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The lifetime-serving priestesses of Hera were female, but Herodotus (Histories, 6.81) referred to a male priest at the Heraion.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: More likely than not, religious specialists would have been Greek.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists were more likely from elite classes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: The priestesses of Hera served life-long terms.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: After the mid-5th century BCE, the city-state of Argos would have had a heavy hand in the administration of the Heraion.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Various decrees of the city-state of Argos have been found in the sanctuary.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No